

THE INTERCULTURALLY COMPETENT TEACHER

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Abstract. *In the age of globalization, teachers need to have special skills to deal with classroom diversity. Classroom diversity is represented by the different cultural, socio-economic backgrounds of the students in a class. The 21st-century teacher should be an interculturally competent person who knows how to address differences among students in a class in a positive manner, as well as manage conflicts and conflict risks successfully. Studies have shown the need to train teachers with respect to several dimensions related to dealing with diversity in class: being and becoming aware of the types of differences among students, ways of positively exploiting differences among students in a class, ways of addressing and managing conflicts based on difference, ways of eliminating discrimination in class. In this paper, we will outline the profile of an interculturally competent teacher.*

Keywords: *intellectual education, cultural environments, cultural diversity, conflict management, intercultural competence.*

COMPETENȚELE INTERCULTURALE ALE PROFESORULUI ÎN EPOCA GLOBALIZĂRII

Rezumat: *În epoca globalizării, profesorii trebuie să aibă abilități speciale pentru a face față diversității clasei. Diversitatea clasei este reprezentată de diferitele medii culturale, socio-economice ale elevilor. Profesorul secolului XXI ar trebui să fie o persoană competentă intercultural, care să știe să abordeze diferențele dintre elevi într-o manieră pozitivă, precum și să gestioneze cu succes conflictele și riscurile de conflict. Studiile au arătat necesitatea de a instrui profesorii cu privire la mai multe dimensiuni legate de abordarea diversității în clasă: a fi și a conștientiza tipurile de diferențe între elevi, modalități de exploatare pozitivă a diferențelor dintre elevi, modalitățile de abordare și gestionare a conflictelor bazate pe diferență, modalități de eliminare a discriminării în clasă. În această lucrare, vom prezenta profilul unui profesor competent intercultural.*

Cuvinte-cheie: *educație intelectuală, medii culturale, diversitatea culturală, gestionarea conflictelor, competența interculturală.*

Competence is a three-dimensional concept; it comprises knowledge, skills and attitudes. Our model of educational intervention relies on providing teachers with training at the level of all the three components of competence. Further, we shall elaborate on what intercultural competence means in terms of knowledge, skills and attitudes.

In terms of intercultural knowledge, content that should be made available to teachers participating in training programs on how to be an interculturally competent teacher able to deal with

classroom diversity should comprise information units focused on:

- ✓ knowledge in socio-human sciences: stereotypes, prejudices, minorities;
- ✓ different teaching strategies based on student cultural capital;
- ✓ cultural identity and intergroup attitudes;
- ✓ strategies of knowledge and inter-knowledge;
- ✓ positive communication and resolution of conflicts.

Teachers aiming to be interculturally compe-

tent and able to address classroom diversity in a positive, productive way must, as J.A. Banks synthesized (1989)[3], be willing to:

1. accept and modify his / her attitudes, conceptions, mentalities, and beliefs;
2. experience new affective experiences;
3. revalorise moral, political and scientific norms and models;
4. reorient their judgments and value judgments;
5. learn new interpersonal behaviours and new interactive styles;
6. learn new strategies of self-knowledge and interpersonal knowledge;
7. be willing to pass these dimensions on to students and others.

The profile of the intercultural competent teacher involves building and manifesting the following professional *skills*:

- *self-reflection*: an effective teacher in a multicultural context will reflect on their own values, stereotypes and prejudices and on how they influence their relationships with students and parents; being aware of their own prejudices, such a teacher will participate in training activities aimed at diminishing preconceived ideas and developing his/her skills in multicultural contexts;
- *the ability to create an appropriate climate*: a competent intercultural teacher appreciates the learning environments that foster active learning, interacts with each student in the class every day, stimulates students through their high expectations for all students, encourages and motivates all students, by means of verbal and non-verbal means (requires students' opinion, maintains visual contact with them, etc.);
- *opting for specific training and leadership strategies*: the intercultural competent teacher favours dynamic group learning, uses collaborative learning strategies, adapts teaching methods and learning content to the cultural potential of students, their learning style and their needs (weaknesses and/or strengths);
- *performing explicit multicultural activities*: providing relevant information about cultural groups through appropriate and informed discussions about race, ethnicity, cultural differ-

ences; exploits in class both differences and similarities; uses various materials and does not use only the manual; critically analyses the teaching auxiliaries in order to eliminate stereotypes and prejudices;

- *ability to build certain types of relationships with parents*: a competent intercultural teacher stimulates parent involvement and shows respect for culture in the families of all students [Nedelcu, 2008, p. 155].

A teacher, before being a teacher, is himself a human being, a person. An intercultural competent teacher is, first of all, a culturally competent person characterized by:

- ✓ the ability to negotiate cultural significance;
- ✓ knowing and integrating multiple alternatives in a personal register;
- ✓ familiarity with the plurality of interpretations and meanings attributed to different cultural facts;
- ✓ the ability to master various linguistic and cultural codes;
- ✓ the ability to work best with new categories (which greatly diminishes anxiety in front of the unknown), to quickly accept them in their own structures;
- ✓ the ability to empathize (cognitive and affective participation in the experience of another person.) [Nedelcu, 2008, p. 158].

Many authors [Swadener, 1988; Sanders & Wiseman, 1990; Ladson-Billings, 1995; Nedelcu, 2004, 2008] include, on the list of qualities of a good teacher, besides pedagogical talent and thorough knowledge in the domain of the discipline, also the intercultural competence, manifested mainly as the *cross-cultural communication ability*: a good communicator establishes interpersonal relationships easily, empathizes, relates lightly to people belonging to other backgrounds, quickly solves communication errors [Giles, Coupland, Williams & Leets, 1991, *apud* Nedelcu, 2008, p. 159]. Also, a teacher who is a good communicator is able to:

- realistically understands the relationship between language and cultural meanings, as well as the ways in which culture gives the form of transmitted messages [Hall, 1966];

– appropriately decodes nonverbal communication as a fundamental component of the message, and this, in its turn, being culturally structured, establishes balanced, equitable and supportive relationships with all students. All these elements are particularly important in the school curriculum because „teaching is, to a large extent, a profession of communication” [Asante, 1992].

Reflection and *self-reflection* are an essential component of intercultural competence within the profile of a good teacher: a reflective practitioner is constantly willing to review, monitor, and improve one’s work, which involves the development of metacognitive strategies to help achieve not only their own practices, attitudes and behaviours, but also their influence on others [Cardelle-Elawar, 1992]. As a reflective practitioner, the competent intercultural teacher understands that his own cultural perspective is not a universal norm, nor is it the only correct one, analysing everything objectively and realistically as a person and practitioner.

A competent intercultural teacher is largely defined by an *active tolerant attitude*.

The higher levels of educational goals are made up of attitudes and values. The formation of affective behaviour involves engaging students in the multi-level landscape of knowledge and culture. To have a certain attitude or feel something, one needs to have a certain understanding of the targeted object. To give one’s opinion about a painting from an exhibition hall, one needs to know many aspects related to the evolution of artistic currents and schools, the phenomenology of the artistic act, to have interacted with many works. To judge one’s kind, one needs to know a lot about the diversity of codes of conduct, ways of being, culture, speaking or personal reasons. To believe in something in an authentic way, one has to believe knowingly (for example, religious belief). To activate values through one’s behaviour, one must have experienced and filtered a vast amount of knowledge and ideas (see Hutmacher’s analyses, 2001). Behavioural value or attitude does not emerge on its own, but relies on a huge ideological and cultural ferment.

An attitude is „a mental and neuropsychic state of preparation, in response to a stimulus,

organized as a result of the subject’s experience and exercising a direct or dynamic influence on the individual’s responses to all the objects and situations to which they relate” [Allport, 1935, *Apud* Fishbein, 1967]. Attitudes reflect the degree of behavioural consistency manifested through special interests and emotional commitment.

Of all the characteristics of attitudes, we mention:

- a) their integrative character, organized in response to a complex stimulus or a situation, as „preparation for an action” (*idem.*);
- b) their directive, intentional nature, outside ordinary logic, expressing a selective orientation, characteristic of the subject. The directive signifies posture, position, and is manifested as observable behaviour;
- c) the intensity of affective, positive or negative engagement with the object can be located on a scale having two poles (positive and negative) and a point 0, meaning neutrality. At the two ends of the scale we have the maximum intensity; as we approach the 0 point, we record different degrees of ease;
- d) centrality translates the degree of internalization of an attitude marked by belonging to a social group, identifying with its values, sharing beliefs;
- e) accessibility means the association between the object of attitude and its affective evaluation and is manifested by the rapidity of the response to the stimulus or the latency of the response.

The functions of attitudes are as follows:

- a) the cognitive function translates through the estimation process, by judging the received data and selecting the obtained operations;
- b) the tonic or energy function provides information about the level of motivation and values, the degree of attitude intensity;
- c) the regulatory function is expressed by the ability to articulate different attitudes in a unifying whole, as a global unit;
- d) the adoptive function is a utilitarian and instrumental function; it means the ability to expect and obtain rewards and reduce „punishments”. By our own attitudes, we try to obtain the acceptance, the approval of others;

- e) the function of expression: through our attitudes we exteriorize our beliefs and central values, we differentiate ourselves from others;
 f) the defence function refers to the individual's effort to maintain self-esteem, to self-protect.

Tolerance as a value and tolerant attitude is reflected in communication; increasing tolerant active attitude can be achieved by acquiring tolerance values and activating them by manifesting behaviour based on active tolerance. Studies in the field of psycho-pedagogy operate with the terms of active tolerance expressed through involvement in life and through actions to achieve the interests of others, attitudes of cooperation and co-participation, respect and a voluntary tendency towards coexistence. In this context, it is necessary to emphasize that the above-mentioned meanings describe in particular the humanism of social relations, characterized by mutual dialogue and understanding, constructive interpersonal communication. *Passive tolerance* means the disadvantaged meanings of tolerance – resistance, indulgence, long acceptance of inconveniences, etc.

The *values and attitudes* of an intercultural competent teacher are:

- ✓ positive valorisation of cultural differences between students in the classroom and beyond;
- ✓ positive attitude towards people and groups

belonging to different cultures that support different values, opinions and beliefs (students and parents coming from different cultural backgrounds);

- ✓ respect for one's own cultural identity and for the cultural identity of others;
- ✓ respect for dignity and human rights;
- ✓ tolerance and understanding;
- ✓ peaceful resolution of conflicts;
- ✓ cultural empathy;
- ✓ civic spirit;
- ✓ availability for intercultural dialogue and cooperation.

Conclusions

Studies have shown the need to train teachers with respect to several dimensions related to dealing with diversity in class: being and becoming aware of the types of differences among students, ways of positively exploiting differences among students in a class, ways of addressing and managing conflicts based on difference, ways of eliminating discrimination in class.

The *active tolerance of teachers* towards students from different cultural backgrounds is characterized by the presence of the following-values, attitudes and behaviour: attention, generosity, self-control, patience, creativity, discretion, empathy, hospitality, availability, dedication, eloquence, respect, objectivity etc.

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